

Emotional Intelligence and Academic Motivation as Predictors of Student Engagement

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Abstract:- This study determined the significant influence of emotional intelligence and academic motivation on student engagement. The quantitative approach using the correlational technique and analysis was utilized in this study with a sample of 300 students from the secondary schools of Manay District, Schools Division of the City of Davao Oriental. Sets of adapted survey questionnaires were used to obtain data from the respondents subjected to content validity and reliability analysis. The data were analyzed using the Mean, Pearson-r, and Multiple Regression Analysis. The results reveal that the emotional intelligence were rated very high, and academic motivation was also rated as very high. At the same time, student engagement was rated very high. Moreover, a significant relationship existed between these variables. A significant relationship between the emotional intelligence and student engagement was not significant. A significant relationship between academic motivation and student engagement was not significant. The extent of the influence of predictor variables on student engagement was proven not significant in the study.

Keywords:- Educational management, student engagement, academic motivation, emotional intelligence, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Learners are not engaging to the highest possible extent especially on teaching-learning activities due to some identified factors such as lack of motivation, bullying, and lack of support and encouragement from teachers. In addition, learners must be encouraged well by their teachers so that their engagement on school activities and programs will be possible (Jankowska & Atlay, 2008).

Engaged students are more likely to complete academic assignments, attend class frequently, and stay in school. Students themselves are probably the best source of information about whether they feel engaged with their teachers and their lessons. Similarly, student engagement is about involving and empowering students in the process of designing their learning experience. It is to ensure that every student has the opportunity to be heard and to know how the school provides learning opportunities (Martin & Bolliger, 2018).

People with high cultural intelligence are confident in their own abilities and are able to adapt their behavior well when interacting with people from other cultures. Cultural intelligence therefore helps students to function effectively in the face of cultural diversity. Cultural intelligence allows students to develop their ability to connect with people and thrive. Desire to be open to new learning experiences (Livermore, 2011).

A study by Rode et al. (2007) predicted that emotional intelligence was related to her academic performance for two reasons. First, academic performance involves a high level of ambiguity. Second, much of the academic work is voluntary and requires a high degree of self-management. Thus, those with high emotional intelligence can perform better academically and strategically prepare viable solutions for advanced student engagement.

One of the most important outcomes of schooling is the development of students' personal and social skills, as well as positive self-concept, self-discipline and self-esteem. Also, students who develop positive relationships with their school community are more likely to become lifelong learners. Most studies of school effectiveness focus on outcomes related to school performance. Much less attention has been given to the extent to which schools engage and engage students in learning and school life, and how this affects student performance and future in school (Fullarton, 2002).

This study intends to provide understanding into the construct of emotional intelligence, academic motivation, and student engagement. There were many studies conducted about decision-making and employees' performance. However, there has been no study conducted yet about the significant influence of emotional intelligence and academic motivation on the student engagement. The researcher presumes that studying the matter could significantly help teach.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

A. Emotional Intelligence

Intelligence is considered one of the most desirable personality traits in today's society. IQ tests are now used in all aspects of society for many purposes, including screening, diagnosis, and evaluation. "It is the most effective predictor of an individual's performance in school and work. They emphasize that successful learning in school depends on many personal qualities, such as perseverance, interest in school and motivation to learn. Along with other cultural factors, academic encouragement

from friends, family and teachers is also important (Gurbuz et al., 2017).

Emotions are involved in everything a person does. every action, decision, judgment. Emotionally intelligent people recognize this and use their thoughts to manage their emotions rather than letting them rule them. Over the last 20 years, the concept of emotional intelligence (EI) has become a very important indicator of an individual's knowledge, skills, and abilities in the workplace, school, and personal life. The overall results of the research suggest that EI plays an important role in job performance, motivation, decision-making, successful management, and leadership. Therefore, applying EI methods to higher education has many benefits for students. It not only satisfies their desires, but increases their efficiency in their field (Alconero-Camarero, 2018).

The first area concerns self-awareness. Emotional intelligence is hypothesized to facilitate positive social functioning by helping individuals perceive the emotional states of others, adopt the perspectives of others, enhance communication, and coordinate behavior. In fact, people with high EQ scores tend to be seen as more socially competent, good at interpersonal relationships, and more sensitive to interpersonal relationships than those with low EQ scores (Caruso, Salovey, Brackett, and Mayer 2015).

In addition, emotional intelligence is thought to help us prioritize our thoughts and help us manage our emotions in anxiety-inducing situations such as driving. B. When participating in standardized testing. Evidence on the role of emotional intelligence in academia is mixed. Some studies show a positive association, while others show no association at all (Mojares, 2015).

Everyone experiences and communicates their feelings and emotions in their daily lives. Emotions contain valuable information about relationships, behaviors, and all aspects of human life around us. Recent research shows that emotions are constructive and contribute to better performance and better decision-making in both work and personal life (Oddleifson, 2019).

His second area of emotional intelligence is dealing with emotions. A particular learning situation that is often characterized by strong student emotions is the feedback situation. Student emotions have a huge impact on how students receive and process feedback. The value of such feedback can be "overshadowed by the learner's reaction." However, few studies have explicitly addressed the role of student emotion in feedback situations (Bloch 2012).

Emotions are not only present in individual actions, but permeate all social interactions. It developed a general theory of emotion in social interactions. It consists of three main arguments. First, he states that all social interactions can be characterized in terms of power and status: your level in a relationship is insufficient, excessive, or adequate. Agencies, or persons in relationships responsible for their level of power, can be distinguished in terms of 'self' or 'other'. Second, certain physiological processes are

associated with varying levels of power and status. For example, there is a direct link between social stress and heart attack ((Barbalet, 2019).

The next area of emotional intelligence is self-motivation. Along with motivation, a commitment to literature is considered very important in improving learning outcomes for all students (Schlechty, 2001; Woolfolk & Margetts, 2007). Motivation is seen as a prerequisite and a necessary factor for student participation in learning. Involvement in student learning is not only an end in itself, but also a means by which students achieve solid academic performance. This is important as it can lead to higher academic performance throughout student life (Van Ta & Zyngier, 2018).

In addition, self-motivation includes personal drive to improve and achieve, commitment to goals, initiative or willingness to seize opportunities, optimism and resilience. Self-motivation and personal time management are key skills in this field. Emotions are strong feelings directed at someone or something and are thought to be important factors in student behavior - (Abdulaziz, Shah, & McCune, 2018).

Traditionally, it has been widely recognized that the emotions and feelings of individual workers play a minor role in their contribution to work and in effective workplace management. Because emotions cannot be smelled, touched, tasted, measured or quantified, this invisible phenomenon has received little attention from managers in the workplace. Management sees emotions as an overly subjective and capricious phenomenon that contributes little to productivity and profits (Bailey, Wang, & , Kaiser 2018).

The fourth domain of emotional intelligence is empathy. Empathy can be expressed in the form of joy, sadness, excitement, misery, pain, and confusion. In healthcare, empathy enables collaboration between healthcare professionals and patients (Miao, Humphrey, Qian, 2017). It is often described as "the ability to see the world through the eyes of others", which simply means developing the ability to imagine what others think and feel in a given situation. (Cooper et al., 2016).

Empathy and trust, on the other hand, are the foundation for building effective relationships, understanding and communication. It is important for generating ideas and solutions, solving problems, communicating effectively, and avoiding or preventing conflicts. Empathy is an important skill that every person must develop to move forward and navigate life (Pedersen et al., 2015).

Once empathy is developed and used, we rarely know exactly what another person is feeling. However, it is important for medical staff to imagine what others are experiencing (Shakir et al., 2017). Communication with others becomes more fruitful when a few basic requirements are met (Gardner, && Qualter, 2009).

Empathy, on the other hand, is a learned ability or attitude toward life that can be used to try to reach out to someone, communicate, and understand the experiences and feelings of others (Mansel, & Einion, 2019). , it is thought that people develop more or less empathy and tend to use this ability more - depending on how they are feeling.

Emotional intelligence forms an important part of nurses' clinical practice. Through emotional intelligence, nurses learn how to deal with their feelings, as well as provide emotional support to patients and their families in multi-dimensional clinical environments. Emotional intelligence is equally important in developing individual's decision-making skills and problem-solving abilities, thereby generally improving the performance of nurses Al-Shakifi, (2015).

Emotional intelligence is made up of a set of skills that lead to a better understanding of one's own feelings and that of others.⁵ It is defined as the ability to identify and recognize the meanings and concepts of emotions, the relationships between them, the reasons behind them, problem-solving based on them, and how to manage emotions (Shuib, Ishak, Amat, .& Ahmad).

The fourth domain of emotional intelligence is social skills. Social skills are defined as interpersonal behavior that helps the individual in society. Social skills are the ability to interact with others that are considered as fundamental to human development (Gershon, & Pellitteri, 2018). Social skills are essential for every social being. These skills are discrete, observable, and teachable behavior that initiate and sustain social interaction and that are decently associated to measures of social competence. (Das, & Ali, 2014).

In addition, social skills help us to connect with others. They streamline our lives and prevent confusion. Gresham & Elliot (1984) noted following three general types of social skills" definitions such as peer acceptance definition which suggest that social skills are those behavior of children and adolescents who are accepted by or are popular with their peers, behavioral definitions which state that social skills are situation specific responses which increase the probability of positive reinforcement and decrease the probability of punishment, and social validity definitions which indicate that social skills are situation-specific behavior which predict and/or correlate with important social outcome (Furnham, Akande, & Callahan, 2004).

Meanwhile, emotional intelligence plays a big role in helping the individuals acquiring the social skills which, in turn, enable them to deal with the social situations. This kind of competence includes the capacity to appropriately respond to all emergency social situations (Mayer, Salovey, & Caruso, 2008). Pekrun, and Linnenbrink-Garcia (2014) pointed out that emotional intelligence is more important to the individual's success in life in comparison with intellectual intelligence, since it plays an

important role in success at work, at study, and in social life (Vogel, & Schwabe,(2016).

Students with emotional intelligence are more popular and well-liked by their friends, and they have high social skills, they are less aggressive, and they are more alert in learning situations. At the home level they are more effective in their life. And at the work level they enhance the team work by helping the others to learn because those students have the capacity of seeing things from the others' points of view and they encourage cooperation during carrying out the educational tasks (Al-Elwan, 2011).

The introductory presentation and discussion of various literature helped highlight the importance of the influence of emotional intelligence on their teaching competence. These served as support to the results and findings of the study.

➤ *Academic Motivation*

There is a multidimensional nature of the work motivation of teachers which can be measured in terms of identified, introjected, and external regulations and amotivation. Positively motivated students influence the study strategy of every individuals and foster academic performance and students well being (Chemolli& Gagne, 2014; Fernet et al., 2008; Guay, et al., 2015).

The first domain is on knowledge. A vast body of literature exists on the relationship of motivation and performance in professional work and organization settings. Motivation is widely acknowledged to enhance performance and efficiency of staff (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Beyond work settings motivation may influence performance in academic settings and among university students (Frey, Homberger, & Osterloh, 2013).

Academic motivation is close to the term 'motivation to learn'. Motivation to learn deals with psychological processes which explain the appearance and involvement of learning activities and its effects. Classical research fields are classroom settings and instruction. Obviously it is also part of academic learning. Learning as well as achieving play certainly a role for motivation to study; learning processes are naturally a part of university education and of academic motivation (Schlieder, Maldonado, & Baltes, 2014).

The second domain is on accomplishment. The lack of motivation in school has been assigned to a mismatch between adolescents' needs and what schools offer (Eccles et al. 1993) and to shifting relevance of life domains for adolescents (Chorney,2017). The mismatch between what students expect from school and what they experience appears to be connected to their affective state. Konings et al. (2011) showed that motivational and concentration problems are related to a mismatch between students' preferences and perceptions of classroom characteristics. In these explanations, the underlying mechanism is the failure to meet students' needs.

The third domain is on stimulation. To improve student performance and motivation in the Dutch context, we designed an innovation based on a combination of extrinsic and intrinsic motivators. A meta-analysis of Cerasoli et al., (2014) showed that a combination of intrinsic motivation and extrinsic incentives is important for performance. Intrinsic motivation predicts quality of performance best, whereas extrinsic incentives are the best predictors of quantity of performance. It was also found that the presence of extrinsic incentives boosted the link between intrinsic motivation and performance (Cerasoli, et al., 2014).

Loewen and Reinders (2017) defined motivation as the desire and incentive of an individual to engage in a specific activity, while Bukhari et al. (2014) referred motivation as students' effort to enhance performance. Meanwhile, motivation towards science learning was defined as students' desire to learn science (Bolat, 2007).

The fourth domain is identified regulation. Identified regulation is characterized as conduct that people perform on the grounds that it is consistent with particular qualities and ideas. Rather than yielding to outside or inward pressures, people experience decision while doing the task, in spite of the fact that the task is not inherently motivating (Gillison, Osborn, Standage & Skevington, 2011; Teixeira, Carraca, Markland, Silva & Ryan, 2012).

Besides, it alludes to doing an This form of internalization is voluntary because one identifies their value or meaning and perceives them as such. Discernment differs from inherent enthusiasm in that the activity is done not out of inherent fulfillment, but because of the instrumental value it speaks of. In this context, it is a form of extrinsic motivation that relies on the autonomous value of a given job. Students with specific motives are considered to be more self-determined than those with extrinsic motives, but are not as completely self-sufficient as those with intrinsic motives (Kim & Cho, 2014).

It happens when behaviors are directed to get a prize or to stay away from any constraints. External motivation signifies that one's conduct is controlled by outer forces, for example, external pressures or financial rewards. It speaks to the most reduced level of self-directed motivation of students (Assor, Vansteenkiste & Kaplan, 2009).

In the same manner, it alludes to doing an action with a specific end goal to get compensation or stay away from reprimands. This type of behavior is said to be non-internalized. Additionally, as external regulation encompasses a sense of coercion and pressure, it characterizes examples of a controlled motivation (Dermody, 2019).

Furthermore, this motivation is related to extrinsic motivation which results from the completion of externally directed rewards, including wages, material assets, reputation, and positive appraisals from other people. Specifically, students' extrinsic motivation comprised

externally directed rewards like compensation, weekly duty and additional allowances (Froiland et al., 2012).

The fifth domain is introjected motivation. Introjected regulation refers to the mode whereby an outer interest turns into an inside representation. Students put weight on themselves through inner intimidation, such as anxiety, guilt, or shame) to ensure that a specific conduct is performed. Similarly, introjected regulation refers to the regulation of conduct because of inside compelling forces, for example, ego-involvement. It said that this type of internalization is usually experienced as controlling (Vansteenkiste, Niemiec, & Soenens., 2010).

In addition, introjected regulation of behavior refers to embracing regulations of behavior but not completely accepting the regulations as your own. This behavior usually characterizes regulation by contingent self-esteem, alluding to ego involvement as a typical form of introjection. This is the type of behavior where individuals feel motivated to exhibit aptitude to uphold self-esteem. Despite the fact that this is internally determined, introjected behavior has an outward observed locus of connectedness. From the time when the connectedness of the behavior is observed as external, the behavior is reflected as non-self-determined (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Murcia, et al., 2008).

Also, introjected directive is thought to be a moderately controlling type of motivation in which behavior is managed by inner authorization and/or weight that are coordinated towards accomplishing reward; for example, sense of self-improvement and pride or staying away from punishment; for example, blame and disgrace. In observational examination, regulation has been connected with transient but not with long haul behavioral perseverance (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Hanover Research, 2014).

However, regulation also characterizes the preliminary step in the adaptive procedure of the internalization of behavior, and hence may assume an essential part in how individuals first come to adopt tasks acquainted with them by others. Indeed, it is contended that without outside influences driving the early phases of behavior change, an individual may not accumulate adequate experience to become competent and acquainted with the new task, a crucial precursor to internalization (Chow, 2013).

The sixth domain is intrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation alludes to perform a task for its innate satisfaction as opposed to for some distinguishable result. When intrinsically motivated, individuals take part in tasks that interest them, and they do as so openly, with a full feeling of volition and without the need for material rewards. Students who are inherently motivated feel that they are doing an action since they have done as such voluntarily and since the activity characterizes a challenge to their prevailing competencies and necessitates them to utilize their creative abilities. This nature of inspiration is regarded as highly self-determined because the reason for

performing the activity is associated exclusively with the person's positive outlook while doing the task (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Skjott Linneberg & Korsgaard, 2019).

Similarly, intrinsically motivated students are said to experience satisfaction and pleasure if they actively perform a certain task or work. Conversely, individuals who have low self-determination are not actively involved in their job and are detached in learning tasks because they perceive such activities as not enjoyable. In the school context, intrinsically motivated teachers are seen to provide a pedagogical setting that positively influences pupils' motivation. As such, some studies confirm the concept that being more intrinsically motivated is associated with more constructive outcomes in the school context (Bear et al., 2017).

Also, motivation is regarded as a stimulant of behavior from a psychological viewpoint. Otherwise it can also be regarded as the tendency of students to develop work effort. The influence of intrinsic motivation on students' experiences is linked with intrinsic rewards they acquire during work. By learning to lead the vital elements of intrinsic motivation, teachers can increase the intrinsic rewards that students develop from work and deliver these categories as choice, competence, meaningfulness and progress (Heery & Noon, 2001; Perlman & Piletic, 2012).

The last domain is amotivation. Amotivated individuals are said to be neither extrinsically nor intrinsically inspired. Amotivation relates to the low level of self-determination. People are amotivated when they have no aim of participating in a specific conduct and don't generally distinguish why they are doing it. Likewise, amotivation is seen as an absence of motivation or yearning as seen in individuals who don't participate in behavior regardless of the number of external stimuli is given (Barkoukisa et al., 2008; Daniels, 2010).

B. Student Engagement

Student's engagement in accomplishing tasks in school varies significantly. Some would consider it as mere requirement to be submitted for a purpose, while others are doing it because it has positive impact on their lives. Pleasurable activities among adults are not perceived similarly by the young people. Adults look at it as activities that provide fun but young ones see it differently that does not address their needs and interests (Dixon, 2015).

In addition, student involvement enhances the student experience, and the time, effort contributed by both the student and the institution to improve and improve student learning outcomes and growth, performance, and reputation, and other related resource interactions (Burch, 2015).

Class community and student engagement are now closely linked (Bryson, 2014). Students who experience a sense of connection and mental and emotional intimacy, rather than isolation, are more prepared to engage in virtual learning and subsequent higher-order thinking and knowledge building (Kahu, & Nelson 2018).

Moreover, individual's attitude in dealing with timeliness and disengagement in learning environment is a common circumstance. It is a matter of individual's choice whether they would see their achievement and be recognized in an instant or keeping it long for them to wait. People deal with the significance of time differently depending on how it affects them in their personal and professional life thus, the school or educational environment can provide resources for the development that improved student participation (Kurucay, & Inan, 2017).

The first domain is on affective engagement. Teachers and peers greatly affect their active participation in classroom instruction. Students who showed positive attitude towards acquiring knowledge and skills in school would practically express fondness on the subject as opposed to those who are less or not interested at all. However, other studies also revealed that these negative attitudes of the students are the results of how they are being treated as members of the school community by their schoolmates, teachers and the school management (Hatch, 2012).

Engagement develops relationships with others and promotes connectedness, but some people with a lower need to belong may be content by few acquaintances (Furlong & Christenson, 2008) while others with a greater need to belong may need many of such contacts. Student engagement is defined as "the time and effort devoted by students to activities that are empirically related to the expected college outcomes, and what the institution does to stimulate student participation in those activities." born (Thomas, 2018).

Emotional involvement includes the student's emotional response or engagement with activities in the learning environment. Cognitive engagement, the focus of this paper, refers to the degree of psychological investment in the learning process exhibited by learners. Recent research includes a fourth component of student engagement.

Agents (Reeve, 2013; Reeve & Tseng, 2011; Sinatra, Broughton & Lombardi, 2014).

The emotional engagement domain concerns questions related to a student's sense of belonging or values (interest, boredom, happiness, sadness, fear, etc.) to a teacher, classroom, or school (Fredricks, & McColskey, 2012).). The second area concerns cognitive engagement. Cognitive engagement is conceptualized in teaching and educational literature as a student's psychological investment in learning. This ranges from memorization to the use of self-regulation strategies to promote deep understanding (Reschly, & Christenson, 2012). Research shows that meaningful learning is based on high-quality cognitive engagement, regardless of educational strategy (Sinatra, & Chinn, 2011).

Cognitive engagement, on the other hand, focuses on the student's internal investment in the learning process. This includes the inherent psychological qualities, or intangible traits, of students that encourage their efforts to learn, understand, and master the knowledge and skills that are embedded in their academic work. (Clary & Zimmermann, 2012).

Similarly, areas of cognitive engagement are selected when examining the investment required for students to understand and master the knowledge and skills that are explicitly taught in school. This lens is important in understanding how student psychological motivation relates to student engagement (Yazzie-Mintz & McCormick, 2012). Among other things, Chickering and Gamson's seven principles include active learning and student-teacher contact, highlighting the importance of cognitive engagement in learning. Deep cognitive engagement is directly linked to achievement (Greene, 2015). To increase cognitive engagement, students need to move from superficial to meaningful cognitive processing (Chi & Wylie, 2014).

Deep cognitive processing enables the kind of mental connection and elaboration of knowledge that facilitates higher-level cognitive learning outcomes, whereas shallow processing perpetuates memory. This is most induced by a lack of robust engagement with learning materials (Heedy et al., 2018).

Another area is behavioral engagement. Behavioral engagement is the observable behavior of students engaged in learning. It refers to student involvement in academic activities and efforts to accomplish academic tasks (Fredricks & McColskey, 2012).

When a student is fully involved in school, he does more than attend class. He contributes positively to the school, not only through classrooms and attitudes, but also through school-related activities that are not necessarily academically based. Student behavior can be a very strong predictor of academic performance. Certain behaviors, such as attendance and completing assignments on time, directly affect grades. Previous studies have found a positive relationship between behavioral engagement and performance outcomes, and a negative relationship between behavioral engagement and discipline problems (Wang et al. 2015).

There was also a strong positive association between participation and school performance, and the resulting positive effects were greater when students engaged in high rather than moderate levels of participation. includes the fact that He also found a correlation between attendance and student performance.

C. Correlation between Measures

Students with high levels of emotional intelligence are more likely to engage behaviorally and emotionally. In addition, we know that students who are more academically active are more likely to be more academically engaged (D'Mello and Graesser 2012).

Students experience a diverse range of emotions during their learning in higher education, such as interest and enjoyment of learning, anxiety, anger, shame, and boredom, all of which have powerful effects on student engagement and learning outcomes (Tulis & Fulmer 2013).

Individuals who are emotionally stable can allocate and utilize their cognitive resources effectively. These resources include attention, memory, and problem-solving, all of which can influence cognitive engagement. Hence, emotional stability can help minimize one's susceptibility to the deleterious effects of negative emotions on cognitive functioning (Perera & DiGiacomo 2013).

High emotional intelligence individuals tend to experience more positive emotions, which can help to motivate and enhance learning. Positive emotions motivate learning as they enhance the interest, enjoyment, and sense of satisfaction derived by individuals during their actual engagement with their tasks. Positive emotions also improve learning by broadening one's cognition and facilitating flexible thinking, creativity, and memory retention (King, & Areepattamanni, 2014).

Emotions can signal socially relevant information to help individuals understand how they can engage and interact successfully with others. Therefore, the ability to read others' emotions accurately not only contributes to opportunities for interactions and maintenance of social relationships, but also helps modify behaviors to respond in socially appropriate ways. Also, individuals with a good understanding of emotions can easily understand people from the perspective of others and show empathy, which is a central characteristic of emotionally intelligent behavior (Mayer, Panter, & Caruso, 2014).

Academic motivation was found to be the most important predictor of academic engagement, more so than student perceptions of teacher support. This study recommends that teachers develop positive relationships with students to support their psychological needs and improve academic engagement and outcomes (Kuh, 2007).

Dornyei (2000) states that even students with high self-efficacy have difficulty understanding the whole unless they actively participate in learning. When Lin (2012) described the relationship between academic motivation and student engagement, he viewed academic motivation as a perception and a kind of discipline that positively or negatively influences a person's behavior.

Students succeed when they are committed to their studies, invest time in learning, and work hard to improve their skills and behaviors. According to related research, one of the most important predictors of academic success is student engagement (Baker, 2004).

In addition, academic motivation is influenced by personal goals, past experience, cultural background, teachers' and peers' opinions of the individual, as well as student involvement. In a study examining the relationship between academic performance and student engagement,

Patrick et al. (2007) discussed the impact of these variables on school performance.

The foregoing related literature and studies cited discussed on the essence of the affective-emotional, cognitive, and affective-behavioral engagement of every learner. These three domains are essential for every learner to be developed in order to be fully equipped with the essentialities.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, we applied a quantitative, non-experimental research design using correlation techniques to determine the significant impact of emotional intelligence and academic motivation on student engagement. of the Davao Oriental Bureau. Quantitative design begins with theoretical analysis, hypothesis formulation, proceeds to theory testing (Caracelli, & Greene, 1993), collects and analyzes data, presents results, develops interpretations, and conducts surveys consistent with the survey questionnaires used. Result generation is included (cited from Creswell, 2014, Chih-Pei & Yan-Yi, 2017). To test the theory that emotional intelligence and academic motivation affects student engagement, in Davao Oriental, this study utilized an adapted survey questionnaire. This research was non-experimental because there were no signs of any manipulation of the predictor variable and data were gathered and measured as they naturally occurred. Thus this research did not contain alteration of any given data. Furthermore, this study applied correlational design in which was utilized by the researcher, correlational statistics to measure and describe the degree of association between two or more sets of scores.

The interest of the study is to investigate the relationship between emotional intelligence and student engagement the relationship between academic motivation and student engagement.

These findings were specific to the context of the public elementary schools of Manay, Davao Oriental. The scope limits the possibility for the overall applicability of the results and the sample; accordingly, even though there could be common structures, the findings may not have overall applicability to other systems.

The public elementary schools of Manay District, Davao Oriental, were chosen as the research setting. The scope limited the possibility for the general applicability of the findings and the sample; accordingly, even though there could be common features, the findings may not have general applicability to other systems.

The respondents of this study are 300 randomly selected Grade 12 students of School A (80), School B (67), School C (46), School D (57) School D (20), School D (20) and School D (20) whose age ranges from 18 – 20 years old. The track from where the respondents are taken was also randomly chosen, and from the total number of Grade 12 students who are officially enrolled in the chosen

track during the school year 2020-2021 in the selected schools, the total number of population was determined.

The researcher sets specific qualifications to qualify for the conduct of the study. As the most mature age group among all high school students, these students are presumed to be matured enough to answer the research question. From the population, the sample from each participating school is determined using the Slovin's Formula to give each Grade 12 student who is in the age bracket considered in the study in these schools to be equally chosen as respondent; simple random sampling is used to determine the final set of respondents.

Specifically, the possible respondents of this research study are the students enrolled in the Senior High School Program of the Department of Education, specifically, Grade 12 in a respondent school aged between 18- 20 regardless of their academic achievement, co-curricular and extra-curricular involvement, and strand. Also, these students are enrolled in both private and public Secondary Schools of Manay Central District. The study excluded all Junior High School, grade 11 and grade 12 students who are below 18 years of age.

On the other hand, in this study, researchers sought to remind respondents that their participation in the study was completely voluntary and that they could opt out without penalty if they wished. You may withdraw your participation if you have any health problems, etc.

Three sets of questionnaires were used to collect data from the respondents. To ensure the accuracy of our measurements, we completed 43 questionnaires.

Subject to analysis of content validity and reliability. Survey instruments validated by external validators with expertise in the fields of social research and statistics. The average rating of the survey by validators is 4.01. Recommended minor revisions to some content and statements in the tool. Before conducting the actual survey, the researchers conducted a preliminary background-check survey of her 50 respondents. The preliminary data collected was subjected to internal consistency testing using Cronbach's Alpha. A 30-item reliability test resulted in a value of 0.877 for the first independent variable, a value of 0.911 for motivation for the second independent variable, and a value of 0.891 for the dependent variable.

In addition, the adapted standardized questionnaire is content valid as it undergoes many modifications to rank the most reliable and valid questions. Moreover, it has already been tested and proven by the author himself. The questionnaire was designed in a highly comprehensive format with the help of expert reviewers so that respondents could easily and conveniently answer each question and understand the purpose of the study. During validation, the questionnaire received an average total score of 4.30. This corresponds to a very good descriptive assessment by expert reviewers.

A pilot test was also conducted. Cronbach alpha is used to check the effectiveness of surveys in the following ways: Cognitive perception and professional commitment to job satisfaction. Cronbach's alpha consistency factor typically ranges from 0 to 1. However, there was no lower bound for the coefficient. The closer the Cronbach's alpha coefficient is to 1, the greater the internal invariance of the items in the scale (Gliem & Gliem, 2003). Changes are made to check the validity of the survey. In addition, the researchers asked the Office of the Superintendent of Manai Davao Oriental for permission to conduct research at various public elementary schools in Manai Davao Oriental. Once approved, a letter of approval will be requested to give the researcher an opportunity to distribute the survey questionnaire to study the respondents. In addition, the researchers sent separate letters to teachers at each school in Manai Davao Oriental to conduct a survey. The researchers asked the principal of the school for permission to distribute the survey questionnaire to each teacher. The researcher personally completed a questionnaire and described the research tool and its purpose. In addition, researchers obtained questionnaires after respondents had answered all items. Finally, the researchers counted and tabulated all the data collected from the respondents and subjected them to statistical analysis. Statistical results are analyzed and interpreted. Conclusions were drawn from the data and recommendations were made based on the research findings.

The statistical tools that are employed by the researcher in the analysis and interpretation of the data are mean which was used to determine the level of emotional intelligence of students, academic motivation of students, and student engagement to answer problems 1, 2, and 3; Pearson r was utilized to determine if the relationship between determine the significant relationship between emotional intelligence and student engagement academic motivation and student engagement. To determine which domain of emotional intelligence and academic motivation best influences the student engagement. And strengthen the obtained result.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data obtained are presented in this part of the work, based on the research goals of this study.

Courses of presentations on the specified topics are: Degree of emotional intelligence, degree of academic motivation and degree of student engagement, correlation between emotional intelligence and student engagement. The relationship between academic motivation and student commitment.

Table 1 shows the average scores on the Emotional Intelligence Index. An overall mean score of 4.50 is considered very high with a standard deviation of 0.09. The very high levels of results show that emotional intelligence is consistently present in the majority of indicators. The overall average quoted is the result obtained from the calculated average value for that metric. From the data, we can conclude that the highest average score of 4.56 or a very high indicator is Emotion Management. On the other hand, the indicator with the lowest average value of 4.33 is still very high and confident.

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Self-Awareness	0.23	4.33	Very High
Managing Emotions	0.17	4.56	Very High
Motivation Oneself	0.17	4.55	Very High
Empathy	0.18	4.53	Very High
Social Skill	0.17	4.55	Very High
Overall	0.09	4.50	Very High

Table 1: Emotional Intelligence

The data show that high emotional intelligence is because respondents highly value the importance of self-confidence, emotional motivation, initiative, empathy, and social skills. These indicators scored very high overall, which is a result of the high scores of teachers. This suggests that students with higher emotional intelligence are better able to control their emotions and empathize with others. This helps students develop improved self-motivation and more effective communication skills, essential skills that enable them to learn more confidently.

Sulaiman & Hassan (2011); Brackett, Warner & Bosco, (2010) found that students with high EQ scores had higher social competence, higher quality of interpersonal relationships, and more interpersonal sensitivity than those with lower EQ scores. said that it tends to be seen as It helps you build stronger relationships, succeed in school and work, and achieve your professional and personal goals. It also helps us connect with the emotions of others, translate our intentions into action, and make informed decisions about what matters most.

The second aim was to determine the level of academic motivation as measured by a survey questionnaire using the following indicators: intrinsic motivation, identified regulation, introduced regulation and external regulation. , and willingness. Table 2 shows the mean values of the research motivation index. The overall mean is 4.46 with a very high standard deviation of 0.16. High-level results indicated that academic motivation was always evident. The overall average quoted is the result obtained from the calculated average value for that metric.

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Knowledge	0.23	4.50	Very High
Accomplishment	0.44	4.38	Very High
Stimulation	0.22	4.52	Very High
Identified Regulation	0.39	4.43	Very High
Introjected Regulation	0.25	4.54	Very High
Extrinsic Regulation	0.31	4.46	Very High
A Motivation	0.35	4.44	Very High
Overall	0.16	4.46	Very High

Table 2: Academic Motivation

From the data, we can infer that the highest average rating of 4.54 or very high indicators are the injected regulations. On the other hand, the metric with the lowest average score of 4.38 is still a very good performer.

The two highest metrics are Introjected Regulation with an average score of 4.63 or very high and Stimulation with an average score of 4.52 or very high.

Additionally, the two highest scores for the regulations introduced indicated that they felt important and that they were intelligent. This indicates that the teacher's students are positively motivated, increasing their enthusiasm for the activity presented. When students are motivated to achieve something by completing a task, they will eventually give it their all and devote their time and energy to it.

This result is consistent with various authors in her Schindler & et al., 2014; Schindler et al., (2014) found that student academic motivation positively influences learning outcomes. Of course, student motivation is related to the student's desire to participate in the learning process. Motivation has a huge impact on effort, learning success, and learning enjoyment. Providing learners with options to engage in new learning, progressing through achievable challenges, and providing feedback on their progress towards their chosen goals will help them maintain their ambitious efforts throughout the school year ahead. can. A third objective was to determine the level of student engagement as measured through questionnaires. Table 3 shows the average student engagement index scores. The overall mean is 4.01, with a standard deviation of 0.32, which is highly appreciated. High-level results indicated that student engagement was consistently demonstrated. The overall average quoted is the result obtained from the calculated average value for that metric. From the

data, we can conclude that the highest average score of 4.53 or a very high index is emotional. In contrast, the index with an average rating of 3.37 or the least recognized. This shows that other students are checking to make sure they don't make the same mistakes themselves. Academic success does not depend on how smart or motivated a student is. But what matters is how they feel about their mistakes so that they can learn from them. indicates that there is The good news in this report is that going to school leads to academic success. It may seem obvious, but constant rumors about bad schools and the failure of the public education system can lead people to believe that missing a few days of school is not so bad. There is a nature. Various authors (Horsch, and Scheele, 2011; Kahu, and Nelson, (2018)) suggest that students should participate in knowledge-building activities in the classroom.

They must be well engaged, and much attention must be given to them on this aspect. Thus, by participating in school activities, students may garner important social competencies which youth may employ to enhance their school connections and academic standing.

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Affective	0.26	4.53	Very High
Cognitive	0.7	3.37	Moderate
Behavioral	0.47	4.15	High
Overall	0.32	4.01	High

Table 3: Level of Engagement Student

Illustrated in Table 4 is the test result on the relationship between the variables. The overall r-value of 0.046 with a p-value of $p = .046$ which was greater than a 0.05 signified the null hypothesis was accepted. It meant that as the emotional intelligence decreases there is also a corresponding decrease on student engagement. This showed that the overall emotional intelligence is not significantly related to student engagement.

All indicators of emotional intelligence when correlated with overall student engagement were not significance. When awareness is correlated with overall student engagement only behavioral with the r value of .029 and a place value of $p < 0.01$, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance set in this study, hence, significant. When managing emotions is correlated with overall student engagement hence, significant except affective with an r value of .042 and a place value of $p = .118$ which is less than the 0.05 level of significance.

Pair	Variables		p-value	Decision on Ho
IV1 and DV	Emotional Intelligence and Student Engagement	.431	0.046	Accept

Table 4: Relationship between the variables

The present study reveals a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and student engagement. This implies that emotional intelligence do not influences student engagement, as seen in the data. These findings

negates the study of Graesser and D'Mello (2012) who said that students who possess high levels of emotional intelligence are more likely to be behaviorally and emotionally engaged. Additionally, we determined that

students who are more academically buoyant are also more likely to experience increased academic engagement.

Shown in Table 4 is the regression coefficient to test the significant influence of the overall of emotional intelligence on student engagement. The model shows that the computed F – value of 1.775 with p=.118 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that emotional intelligence had an overall not significant influence on student engagement. The overall result revealed that student engagement and academic motivation since it showed a negative result on the significance level which is higher than the boundary limit of 0.05. For further analysis, it indicates that that

engaging students in the learning process increases their attention and focus, motivates them to practice higher-level critical thinking skills, and promotes meaningful learning experiences.

This finding contradicts the proposition espoused by (Sulaiman & Hassan, 2011) who stressed that emotional intelligence is conducive to affective engagement. students who frequently experience positive emotions tend to perceive positive events as more likely to occur than negative events, thereby encouraging engagement by formulating a wider variety of future plans for themselves

Student Engagement				
Emotional Intelligence	B (Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	T	Sig.
Constant	4.470	.885	5.052	.000
Self-Awareness	-.050	-.067	.839	.402
Managing Emotions	-.113	-.208	1.838	.067
Motivation Oneself	.145	.270	2.360	.019
Empathy	-.026	-.045	.438	.662
Social Skill	-.030	-.053	.500	.618
R	.171			
R ²	.029			
F	1.775			
p	.118			

Table 5: Significance on the Influence Emotional Intelligence and Student Engagement

Shown in Table 6 is the Academic Motivation and Student Engagement, Presented in Table 6 are the results of the significance test on the relationship between the variables involved in the study. The overall r-value of -0.028 and a p=.629 signified the null hypothesis acceptance. It meant that there is no significant relationship between academic motivation and student engagement. When all indicators of academic motivation when correlated with the overall student engagement all of the r-values are greater than p<0.05 significant level hence, not significant. When accomplishments correlated with overall student engagement hence not significant except behavioral with an r value of .269 and a place value of p < 0.01 which is less than the 0.05 level of significance set in this study, hence, significant.

The overall result of this study revealed that the domains of academic motivation which significantly influence student engagement. Therefore, motivation is seen as a pre-requisite of and a necessary element for student engagement in learning. Student engagement in learning is not only an end in itself but it is also a means to the end of students achieving sound academic outcomes. In the same manner, the results show congruence with the findings of that Lin, (2012); Baker (2015); Patrick et al. (2007) who posit that Student engagement recognizes the complexity of engagement across cognitive, behavioral, affective, or

affective domains and includes contextual variables (such as individual and family It accepts individuals historically positioned within given moment) is in their learning.

The results of this study supported the statement of Fernet et al. (2008) he found that faculty engagement and engagement are essential to the successful implementation of strategic change in an organization. It can be said that companies can ask employees to make strategic changes involving as many managers and employees as possible. This study also supports the thesis of Assor et al., (2009). The thesis states that teaching style is also related to trust in students and understanding of the purpose of education in general. Teachers who practice this style serve as helpful mentors and are tolerant of their students. Teachers also believe in the best way for students to learn about learning.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

Several recommendations are made based on the above findings and conclusions. With very high levels of emotional intelligence, very high levels of academic motivation, and high levels of student engagement, students with high levels of emotional intelligence are more likely to engage behaviorally and emotionally. In addition, we found that students who were enthusiastic about their studies were more likely to be involved in their studies.

The significant relationship recommended that the policymakers, particularly the officials from the Department of Education, review and revisit their existing educational policies to find out if they address the demands and challenges of being a 21st-century educator, mainly focusing on how to heighten student’s emotional intelligence and academic motivation, hence, also improving their student engagement.

Finally, future studies toward examining other variables that can possibly influence between emotional intelligence and academic motivation which will be of utmost importance to the research community shall be taken into consideration.

Consequently, the level of student engagement is also very high in terms of affective-emotional and high level cognitive, and behavioral. It is important to increase students’ cognitive and behavioral engagements.

Furthermore, it would be beneficial to the students if their parents set as good example and help them in their study and give their full support as they served as the first teacher at home. Above all, the students should be more flexible in handling emotional intelligence situations in eradicating negative attitudes towards learning.

Academic Motivation	Student Engagement			
	Affective	Cognitive	Behavioral	Overall
Knowledge	-.014 (0.813)	.015 (0.802)	.037 (0.519)	.026 (0.654)
Accomplishment	.005 (0.925)	-.054 (0.355)	.269* (0.000)	0.091 (0.116)
Stimulation	.028 (0.629)	-.005 (0.929)	-.046 (0.431)	-.019 (0.738)
Identified Regulation	.123* (0.033)	-.044 (0.452)	.016 (0.783)	.006 (0.917)
Introjected Regulation	.034 (0.553)	.048 (0.403)	-.012 (0.834)	.041 (0.480)
Extrinsic Regulation	.062 (0.286)	-.169* (0.003)	.061 (0.289)	-.088 (0.130)
A Motivation	.193* (0.001)	-.101 (0.079)	.088 (0.127)	.016 (0.779)
Overall	.133* (0.022)	-.102 (0.078)	.149* (0.010)	.028 (0.629)

Table 6: Significance on the Relationship between Academic Motivation and Student Engagement

VI. CONCLUSION

As can be seen from the results of this study, this section draws conclusions. The results of this study support the hypothesis that student engagement mediates the impact on the relationship between self-concept and learning motivation. The results of this study correspond to the Isen 2000 statement. King & Gaerlan (2014) that high emotional intelligence individuals tend to experience more positive emotions, which can help to motivate and enhance learning. Positive emotions motivate learning as they enhance the interest, enjoyment, and sense of satisfaction derived by individuals during their actual engagement with their tasks. Positive emotions also improve learning by broadening one’s cognition and facilitating flexible thinking, creativity, and memory retention. It also validates the claim of (Mayer et al., 2003) that emotions can signal socially relevant information to help individuals understand how they can engage and interact successfully with others. Therefore, the ability to read others’ emotions accurately not only contributes to opportunities for interactions and maintenance of social relationships, but also helps modify behaviors to respond in socially appropriate ways. Also, individuals with a good understanding of emotions can easily understand people from the perspective of others and show empathy, which is a central characteristic of emotionally intelligent behavior

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